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Comics: medieval illuminations as Sequential Art

Quadrinhos: as iluminuras medievais como Arte Sequencial

Lula Borges¹

ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this research is to present medieval illuminations as sequential art and to examine whether this artistic form contains elements of comics in its structure, qualifying it as sequential art, and identifying these elements. The study also involves a comparison between the secular art of illuminations and contemporary comic art, focusing on Prince Valiant, a character created by Hal Foster, as a significant example. The objective is to determine whether the same sequential art elements used in the protagonist's comics are present in medieval illuminations. The research is based on bibliographies commonly related to comics, with references to classic authors in this field. Barbieri (2017), Eisner, 1985, McCloud (1995), Groensteen (1999), and Diniz, Eder (n.d.) were consulted for discussions on comics, while Visali and Godoi (2016) were referenced for illuminations. Andrade (2017) was primarily consulted for Prince Valiant. However, other authors were included in the theoretical framework of the study. Additionally, research was conducted in a codex library (E-Codices) to verify the evolution of illumination art and its gradual yet continuous shift towards Sequential Art.

Keywords: Comics. Medieval illuminations. Prince Valiant. Sequential Art in the Middle Ages.

RESUMO

O objetivo deste artigo é apresentar as iluminuras medievais como Arte Sequencial e, como tal, verificar se esse tipo artístico tem elementos dos quadrinhos em seu corpo, para ser considerada como tal forma artística. Dessa pesquisa, para uma comparação com a arte secular das iluminuras dentro dos códices, existe também uma comparação com a arte atual dos quadrinhos, elencando-se o “Príncipe Valente” como estudo de caso para ver quais elementos dos quadrinhos, utilizados no personagem são utilizados também nas iluminuras medievais. A pesquisa é elaborada em bibliografias que perpassam as que são normalmente voltadas para as Histórias em Quadrinhos; no entanto, será utilizado também os autores clássicos desse tipo de estudo. Dentre os pesquisadores, para a base teórica do trabalho foram utilizados Barbieri (2017), Eisner (1985) McCloud (1995) Groensteen (1999), Diniz e Eder (Sem Data) para expor o assunto quadrinhos; Vianna (2016), Visali e Godoi (2016) para tratar do assunto Iluminuras e Andrade (2017), principalmente, para discorrer sobre o Príncipe valente. No entanto, outros autores foram elencados para o arcabouço teórico do trabalho.

Palavras-chave: Histórias em Quadrinhos. Iluminuras medievais. Príncipe Valente. Arte Sequencial na Idade Média.

Beginning

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate that medieval illuminations (a visual representation mode inserted in parchment, papyrus and later codices, books that presented stories that spoke of the lives of saints and sponsors in general such as kings or great merchants of that time), can be

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seen, in many cases, as sequential art which, in our reality, is synonymous of Comics. The justification is that elements of comics were inserted in the miniaturized productions of the Middle Ages, thus transforming that type of art, where drawings or florals were inserted around the page, into Sequential Art, with its own language focused on linear understanding within the images and texts created in the millennium of the Middle Ages.

For a more complete understanding of the text, it is necessary to also address current comics, their elements, their history in art and human history, and draw parallels with illuminations from contemporary materials focused on the art of comics. In this way, it is possible to establish a connection between what we know as Comics and what has already been produced as Sequential Art in that historical phase.

Therefore, this text has four primary steps that must be observed. The first is to talk about the elements of Comics; then a significant example study with the character Prince Valiant, by Hal Foster, about the use of comic book elements in his stories; then a study on illuminations, their history, their development and finally a subchapter which addresses the question on which this article is elaborated: are medieval illuminations Sequential Art?

1. SEQUENTIAL ART, THE COMICS

Comics is also known as Sequential Art. The term was coined by Will Eisner in 1985 and dates back to the first edition of "Comics and Sequential Art". It has been defended by scholars around the world since then. After all, this is a type of art that must have a sequel to be read and enjoyed. It is a type of reading that was officially created by the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. In its production, recognizable drawings and texts are normally needed, where there is a "verbal-visuality" relationship (XAVIER, 2019), despite the fact that the text element is not mandatory when reading this type of narrative. Another characteristic is that it is a mass media, according to social concepts, which a large part of the graphic mythology of the twentieth century is associated with, with examples like Mickey, Superman, Flash Gordon, Tarzan, among others, as a form of mass perception of population of many, if not all, countries.

It is interesting to note that the term Comics has many different names in the various countries in which it is used. Different names are used, even in countries that speak the same language, such as Portuguese, where in Brazil the term *Histórias em Quadrinhos*, (translating is like comics in frames or histories in little frames, because the comics have this characteristics), but in Portugal, for example, *Banda Desenhada* is used, an approximation with terms used in France (*bandes dessinées*), Belgium and Switzerland. In Angola, the term is *Histórias aos quadrinhos* (history in squares) which is closer to the Brazilian term. Other names are used, such as Comics,

which emerged in the United States and has spread to several other countries, even those that do not speak English. In others who use the Anglophone language, they also have the terms *Komiks* or *strokiesprente* in Indonesia and South Africa, respectively. Other names such as *Fumeti* (Italia), *Manga*, *Manwa* (in any asian countries) appear in several other countries and several other languages around the world².

However, despite the amorphous terms for the same type of art, these same countries accept and defend the term Sequential Art. For a more accurate understanding, wherever there are studies on comics, at least as far as my ongoing research points out, when talking about Sequential Art or, in different languages, Arte Sequencial (Brazil), Arte Secuencial (spanish language), arte sequenziale (Italy), art séquentiel (France) among others local linguistic modifications, the term is accepted and understood as Comics, facilitating the understanding of what one wants to defend on the various subjects that researchers may publish; although there is nothing to prevent that, when speaking the regional term “comics”, it does not block the understanding of the topic that is written by any researcher.

Sequential Art encompasses elements beyond the mere combination of images and text. The frame (or dividing line that constitutes each panel) serves as one such element (several panels come together to form a narrative). The gutter, it is the space between these panels, Additionally, the choices of shots and angles in the illustrations are employed to emphasize the storytelling (BARBIERI, 2017). Another component worth noting is the overlay, which refers to a visual element that spans across multiple panels on the same page. Further elements to consider include the Splash page, Timing, character framing, and more. In essence, there exists a comprehensive visual language that can be studied in greater depth through Will Eisner's book, “Comics and Sequential Art” (1989), which delves into these concepts. Any reader interested in exploring these elements further can find in Eisner’s work.

During the explanation of “Timing”, Eisner (1989, p. 25) states that time in comics is equivalent to the space occupied by the comic. As demonstrated in his work, a comic book can contain more or fewer panels or pages, depending on the decisions made by the writer and, subsequently, the artist when arranging elements on the page. For instance, one character can shoot another, and the action can be conveyed in just two or three panels, or additional panels can be utilized to place greater emphasis on that particular moment.

Scott McCloud (1995) asserts that comics, as Sequential Art, have a defined limit of frames. Starting with just two frames, we can classify it as a comic. Therefore, a comic book is a form of Sequential Art. A comic strip, which typically features stories with a beginning, middle, and end,

² There are much sites about comics terms around the world, we choosen this <https://www.infoplease.com/awards/film/international-glossary-comic-terms> . Access in 12/10/2023

often consists of an average of three frames. However, there can be strips with four frames or even more, although surpassing that number is rare, or even fewer frames, as low as two, and it's still considered a comic book. However, if there's only a single panel telling a certain event, even with a frame, speech bubble, image, or movement, it does not qualify as a comic. However, there are authors who measure this type of art as comics too, as is the case of Guimarães (1999) who discusses the limits of what can be a comic book, for example.

Regarding the text in comics, Eisner (1985), starting on page 122, discusses several situations in which text is a part of the comic book. According to the author, the elements of drawing and text are inseparable within a comic narrative. However, there are sequences in which text is not necessary, as the images speak for themselves, with “various possible applications of text which include dialogue, connecting narrative and description” (Eisner, 1985, p. 125). Screenwriters always find a way to add text, but, as mentioned above, this element is not essential.

Traditionally, the place where texts are placed is in speech balloons. This is one of the essential elements of comics and dates back to October 30, 1896, with Richard Felton Outcault's "The Yellow Kid" strips as the starting point of modern comics (Paz, 2018). However, other authors consider this date to be "artificial" (McCloud, 1995, p. 199) since comics existed in various parts of the world before the proclamation of this date, as we will see throughout this text. The balloon is typically in an elliptical shape and the text is placed inside it, with a tail pointing towards the character who is speaking or thinking (BARBIERI, 2017). In fact, the ellipse, which is the body of the balloon, doesn't necessarily have to be elliptical. There are various ways to represent this balloon, such as normal speech, whisper, shout, robotic speech, and thought, each with its specific presentation characteristics within the panels.

Other times, there are only captions in text boxes, explaining what is happening in the scene, before or after what happens in it, after all, we are talking about Sequential Art. Readers are used to reading the subtitles, normally, above what is happening in the scene, but, depending on what is happening on a page, the subtitles can be next to or below the image. There are several Comics that use this element to describe what happens in the scene, or even what a character thinks, while the drawing aims to balance this artistic form (Visali, Godoi, 2016). Everyone who works with comics has certainly used many sequences with just subtitles or even no text at all.

2. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PRINCE VALIANT

However, there is a comic book that is paradigmatic for the issue of the *corpus* of Sequential Art: Prince Valiant. The choice of character is due to the fact that the character is set in the medieval

period, dealing with themes related to it, in addition to the characteristic of being a graphic narrative that, for more than eighty years, never used another form of communication with its audience except for images and captions, without the characteristic speech balloons. This is because have never been used in Valiant's stories, although, since the mid-2010s, some of them have started to use this element in some series outside the traditional Sunday production, which continues not to use speech balloons, resembling the context of medieval codices, with only images and text around, in the case of the prince, captions.

Knight stories are some of the most engaging tales for many civilizations, especially the older ones. Horses have been used since animal domestication and serve for carrying loads, plowing, and transportation. This is still the case in many countries today. In the imagination of several of these societies, the horse is primarily a symbol of power (Andrade, 2017). It has been depicted with wings, at sea, amalgamated with people, with horns; to represent the narratives of those peoples. Even with the use of machines like trains or automobiles in modern times, stories of more contemporary knights like cowboys or rangers fill the thoughts of the general population.

But when it comes to chivalrous stories, medieval knights come to mind, and among them, the legends of the Templars, Crusades, or battles within tournament areas in splendid castles. Of these stories, that of King Arthur is certainly the most well-known, the most captivating, the one that has spread the most in the popular imagination. Stories of chivalry began in European codices and oral tradition since the 11th century. Meanwhile, the legend of King Arthur is a historical or narrative parallel to Charlemagne, the king who united several kingdoms into one during the spread of Christianity in Europe at that same age. Arthur, who was a warrior leader, becomes the supreme king, ruling over various realms.

The beginning of the dissemination of Arthurian legends occurs with Geoffrey of Monmouth in *Historia regum britannie* (1136), where Arthur stops being a chief and becomes a supra-King, ruling from Scandinavia to Rome, drawing a parallel and rivaling with Arthur himself. Charlemagne. Chrétien de Troyes, in the 12th century, made Arthur a supra-King, but under the feudal model, creating several works based on Arthurian imagery. Between the 12th and 13th centuries, Robert de Boron Christianizes and sanctifies the Grail in the narrative. (ANDRADE, 2017, p. 22)³

According to Andrade (2017), several other writers have worked on the evolution of the character Arthur or the Arthurian narratives and his Knights of the Round Table, doing so even today, with stories that are used in various types of media, such as comics, including science fiction,

3 Free translating of: O início da difusão das lendas arturianas se dá com Geoffrey de Monmouth em *Historia regum britannie* (1136), onde Artur deixa de ser um chefe e vira um supra-Rei, governando desde a Escandinávia até Roma, traçando um paralelo e rivalizando com o próprio Carlos Magno. Chrétien de Troyes, no século XII, fará de Artur um supra-Rei, mas sob o modelo feudal, criando diversas obras baseadas no imaginário arturiano. Entre o século XII e o século XIII, Robert de Boron cristianiza e santifica o Graal na narrativa.

as is the case with Camelot 3000 (BARR, BOLLAND, 1982-85), radio plays, cartoons, new books and movies that talk about the king himself, his knights, Merlin, Morgana le Fay or their quests for magic or the Holy Grail.

Among the various possible stories related to the Regent, emerges that of Prince Valiant, an addendum to the story of King Arthur, or spin-off - that is, a work derived from another already existing or exploring characters that have emerged in other works -⁴, in which Valiant meets this king and ends up being one of the Knights of the Round Table. The story of the Prince arises from the invasion of his father's lands, who flees with a small entourage from his kingdom and arrives at a swamp, where he lives with what could be called savages, for having a less civilized life; from there, Valiant develops his skills, leaving the swamp after a few years and getting involved in various adventures, in which he meets King Arthur, receives demands from him, gets involved with other knights and with Merlin and Morgana le Fay. Over time, he gets married and has children. There is still no end to Valiant's stories, as they are told to this day (figure 1).

Figure 1: Detail of the current published page of Prince Valiant. Highlight for the date, within the week I create this text.

<https://comicskingdom.com/prince-valiant/2023-03-05>. Retrieved March 5, 2023.

4 Significados. *Spin-off*. Retrieved March 2, 2023, from <https://www.significados.com.br/spin-off/>

The author of the work is Harold Rudolph Foster, or, as he is better known, Hal Foster, born in Halifax, Canada in 1892 and died in Florida, United States in 1982 at the age of 90. Foster was already well known to the public when Valiant was created. He had always been self-taught and had worked as an advertising executive, boxer, and forest ranger. In 1929, he began drawing the stories of *Tarzan of the Apes*, which were well received by readers. At that time he already had some ideas for making medieval stories, but out of necessity, he made the Sunday strips of Edgar Rice Burroughs' character. According to Andrade (2017), Foster did not want to continue creating the adventures of the "King of the Jungle" and even gave up making the strips; but due to the stock market crash, fans (and even Burroughs) wanted him as the artist of strips and due to the need for work, he continued to make Tarzan comics until 1937.

In that year, he presented the stories of Prince Valiant, which began to be published and were soon accepted for the quality of the work (figure 2). From then until his death in 1982, Hal Foster worked only on this piece, doing the scripts and drawings. In 1971, he passed the drawing to other artists and in the early 1980s his son began writing the character's script. Two years later, the creator of Prince passed away.

Figure 2 - Detail of the first page of Prince Valiant. Highlight for the original publication date, on Feb 13, 1937.

Source: Author's edition (2023). Prince Valiant 01 - 1937-1939. [PDF file]. Retrieved from <https://archive.org/details/prince-valiant-01-1937-1939/page/n111/mode/2up> at Mar 01, 2023.

As mentioned, since its creation almost 90 years ago, Prince Valiant's stories have no speech balloons, despite having all other elements. This sequential art work is acclaimed by comic book readers and critics. As mentioned too, there are also texts, panels, drawings, timing, and action, but no speech balloons. Only captions. Various comic book authors, such as McCloud (1995), for example, argue that it does not need to have balloons to be sequential art. There are several comics that do not have this element.

Well, there's a small question in the air: if comics must have text and images and this text is placed in specific locations within graphic narratives, and if there are comics that don't use text, would Hal Foster's work would no longer be comics because it doesn't have speech balloons? No! Prince Valiant is a comic. It is sequential art. With this question answered, at least for now; I move on to another subject of this article: the illuminations made from the end of the ancient age, around the 4th century, and throughout the Middle Ages.

3. MEDIEVAL ILLUMINATIONS

The recording of fictions and historical facts holds a significant importance for the history of humanity. It is through these writings that we learn about what occurred in a particular past civilization or what is desired for the future. However, when illustrating what is written, reading gains greater significance because, in addition to what is conveyed in the texts, there are illustrations, whether they be drawings, paintings, details (often floral or friezes), or even tapestries and bas-reliefs (Groensteen, 1999). These illustrations enhance the appreciation of what is read, as they amplify the content of the written word. The connection with images makes the reading more comprehensible, both for the readers of the time and for posterity, as it allows for a visual sharing of the experiences described in the text, providing a more detailed insight into the era when the work was created (VISALI and GODOI, 2016).

These writings have evolved throughout history, up to our present time. Today, we utilize screens, touch interfaces, keyboards, and various fonts to enhance our reading experience. However, it has been a journey through various stages, including materials such as stone, beaten clay, animal skins, and papyrus, which were used until the Christian Era in the West. Primarily, it was from the Middle Ages onward that a new transformation revolutionized the way works were written and meant to be read: codices, a primitive form of a book. The texts within codices were initially associated with the Catholic Church, but over time, they expanded to encompass events in the lives of kings, princes, the aristocracy, and wealthy merchants of that era. This type of book began to develop from the 2nd century, initially containing only written text, and later incorporating some images, primarily decorative ones such as floral motifs and friezes around the page. These images are known as *illuminations*.

Only after several centuries was the figurative use of images permitted. The prohibition of imagistic reproduction in the medieval era can be explained by the fact that, although an image serves as a representation in our reality, in medieval society, "imago" (from Latin) signified "similarity" (Visali & Godoi, 2016). The image was regarded as the very thing it represented, as if

the representation of a man were the man himself. Anthropologically, this can also be observed in primitive societies, and in the Bible, we have the example, "Let us make man in our image, after our likeness" (Gen. 1, 26), meaning, how can one represent Christ if the image of Christ was Christ himself? This notion was considered heresy by many clergy around Europe.

In the 6th century, Pope Gregory the Great initiated a change in attitude toward images, stating that this form of publication was intended to "teach, remind, and move" (Visali & Godoi, 2016, p. 131). Medieval society was largely illiterate, and images helped the clergy better convey their messages to their followers. Despite the church's initial iconoclasm, Gregory's writing was so widely disseminated that images eventually gained acceptance in sacred publications, leading to an increasing production of illuminations during various reigns. Some of these works were referred to as the "Bible of the illiterate" (Visali & Godoi, 2016, p. 131), which boosted the demand for the Christian faith.

It's important to note that over time, in addition to the Bible, there were also stories depicting the lives of saints, customizing what was published for a duke, a king, a bishop, and with the completed work, one could offer an expensive gift like these types of books. These books were highly welcomed in various monasteries and palaces, gradually increasing the quantity of books in these locations, eventually reaching an estimated 50,000 manuscripts copied in the 9th century (Visali & Godoi, 2016, p. 138).

Miniators or scribes, who were typically religious individuals in monasteries, handled both the writing and the artwork in productions until the 6th century. However, over time, professional artists dedicated themselves primarily to the illustrative part of manuscripts, which was a costly endeavor requiring time and skill to create. Upon receiving such a gift, the recipient felt honored by the giver's appreciation. Some of these patrons also began to have codices with their own stories, in addition to kings, princes, and prominent figures in communities who could afford them. The history of King Charlemagne or his representation alongside King Arthur underscores the significance of these sponsorships (Visali & Godoi, 2016).

Technically, illumination is the result of painting (or drawing) images on a medium such as paper, parchment (animal leather), or papyrus, for the writings of that era. Scrolls made from parchment and papyrus had to be unrolled to read their contents and then rolled back up for storage. Starting in the 1st century AD, a simpler form of viewing documents that weren't scrolls emerged. They began cutting them into rectangular shapes, creating folios, or sheets of leather or papyrus. These folios were stacked on top of each other and bound together, with a thicker sheet, typically made from pieces of wood or tree bark, added after assembly to secure the pages and close it, thus creating the codex (from the Latin "caudex" or tree bark). Creating a codex often required the

sacrifice of entire herds of animals to make use of their leather (Visali & Godoi, 2016). Codices, due to the manual writing factor, varied in size, but on average, they measured from 20 to 35 cm in width or height (see figure 3).

Figures 3 and 4 - Two distinct codex pages, one from the 7th century with only ornamental elements, and another from the 12th century with a significantly developed narrative.

e-codices: Virtual Manuscript Library of Switzerland. (2023). Retrieved from <https://e-codices.unifr.ch/en>

There are three elements in the production of these pages: the text, which in the early centuries was handwritten; the signs, such as ornaments, pictograms, ideograms, initials, or capital letters - which were letters used in stone to designate locations, official environments, squares, friezes, and florals; and the illuminations themselves, more elaborate drawings with a tendency toward figurative representation. The earliest codices contained only text and no drawings. The illuminations, along with the signs, began with few drawings in each manuscript. However, from the 10th to the 11th century, the work developed to the point where there were schools and styles for the production of these works. Text was placed at the bottom of the page, with the rest of the page featuring an illustration of what had been written. At this point, we can recall the work of Prince

Valiant, as that's precisely how the pages of this character are structured. The images in Figures 3 and 4 show two illuminations from the 7th and 12th centuries, demonstrating that development brought more images with greater detail, as well as more elaborate techniques of writing, iconography, and figurative art, resulting in higher visual quality for the produced pages.

4. THE ILLUMINATIONS AS SEQUENTIAL ART

To provide further information, research was conducted on the chronology of codices to understand from which era illuminations began to be produced and when they started to be placed sequentially. Several questions were raised during this investigation. What elements from comics were used? Were there captions, speech bubbles, dialogues, motion, timing? Can these elements be listed, or not, as a form of sequential art?

Regarding the research *locus*, the E-codices⁵ website, a Swiss site specifically designed for codex inquiries, was investigated. The site can be viewed in German, English, French, and Italian. When conducting a search, users have the option to select the author's name, work, country, but primarily, the century, greatly facilitating chronological searches. Other distinct fields include whether the codex contains illuminations or not, whether it's a manuscript or mechanically written, whether it has annotations, and its language (Hebrew, Greek, Christian), among more than a dozen other options. There are over two thousand works that can be accessed on the E-codices website.

Ao pesquisar, o internauta tem a possibilidade de escolher nome de autor, obra, país, mas principalmente, o século, facilitando muito o que se buscar cronologicamente. Outros campos distintos são: se o códice tem iluminura ou não, manuscrito ou escrita mecânica, anotações ou não, hebreu, grego, cristão, entre mais de uma dezena de possibilidades de escolhas e mais de duas mil obras, que podem ser acessadas no site E-codice.

When selecting by century, the earliest codex available starts from the 4th century, where there is only one book, which is a fragment of some ancient Syrian books, written in Greek, including gospels and epistles, and in very poor preservation condition, according to E-codices. It lacks images, and the texts, as mentioned, are fragments, pieces, torn pages, without the possibility of effective reading⁶. Apparently, the earliest known codex is the Codex Sinaiticus⁷, also apparently from the 4th century. It's worth noting that before this, only fragments and parchments were found,

5 e-codices: Virtual Manuscript Library of Switzerland. (2023). Retrieved from <https://e-codices.unifr.ch/>

6 e-codices: Virtual Manuscript Library of Switzerland. (2023). Retrieved from <https://e-codices.unifr.ch/en/searchresult/list/one/fmb/cb-0024>

7 Codex Sinaiticus. (2023). Retrieved from <https://codexsinaiticus.org/en/>

and E-codices exclusively deals with codices. Thus, it was preferred to continue the search using this website.

The production of only text in pages continues in other works in the 5th century, although the first illuminations emerge during the search. The first of them is the *Abba-Abacus Glossary in the form of a palimpsest*⁸, a glossary with translations from Latin and Psalms. In the entire book, there is only one image, apparently of a saint with a scholarly appearance, words surrounding him, and various signs around the page, mainly in a checkerboard pattern.

In the same way, productions from the subsequent centuries feature texts, florals, initials, along with some books on astrology and astronomy, each accompanied by their respective illustrations. After the 8th century, the realism in the images becomes more apparent. Finally, in the 9th century, a book with numerous allegorical illustrations about the physiology of animals and plants, a small narrative with many images, in which a sequence can be perceived, along with explanations below them. It is possible that the perception of sequential images began to emerge in illustrated production around this time. However, it is in the 10th century that a more detailed form of sequential art becomes noticeable.

"Carmina, Prudentius" or "Poems of Prudentius" demonstrates many characteristics of comics, or sequential art. The work is a collection of poems with religious and moral themes, hymns, the martyrdom of saints, Christian conduct, and the allegory "Psychomachia", a poem that presents the struggle of the seven vices and the seven virtues for a human soul as a battle between these forces, commanded by angels and demons, in which victory is achieved by the virtues. Below, we see three of these passages (Figure 5), possibly depicting wrath against patience, pride against humility, and gluttony against temperance (Nogueira, 2015).

Figure 5 – Passages from "Carmina Prudentius"

Source: Available at: <https://e-codices.unifr.ch/en/list/one/bbb/0264>

When observing the pages, the resemblance to a comic book becomes evident, with meta-panels spanning a page, captions around, above, beside, and below them. On page 65, there are also some lines above the heads of the angels, as if they were speaking to the characters in the tent. Could this be a premise for speech balloons? In fact, in other works, speech balloons are also demonstrated. Although they are incipient and initial, they are noticeable to researchers or even comic book readers. Take Figure 6, for example, where the progression of dialogue and even speech balloons with tails (Figure 6B) is observable over the centuries. Similarly, in Figure 6C, even though the balloon bodies and tails are absent, the "speech" of the characters can be perceived. An interesting fact is recognizing the phylactery as a speech element in this 13th-century work (Figure 6A), depicting the conversion of the Apostle Paul (Diniz, Eder, n.d.).

Figure 6 - Various pages from works predating modern comics. The works are without initial references as the sources from which they were obtained are missing.

Source: Diniz, Eder, n.d.

It is evident that art absorbs elements from life or other artistic creations and converts them into a new language. For instance, this is the case with phylacteries, which are ribbons with various phrases, typically of a religious nature. When absorbed by visual arts, they take on another symbolic meaning. In illuminated manuscripts, for example, they transformed into the speech of characters that appear in narrative sequences.

During the Middle Ages, phylacteries found their way into visual arts in the form of ribbons with messages or prayers written in sacred paintings. Typically, a saint or an angel would be their bearer. [...] This example is from the year 1240 and depicts the conversion of the Apostle Paul. From this point forward, what occurs is a gradual shift from phylacteries to attempts to incorporate texts spoken by the characters into the artwork⁹ (Diniz, Eder, n.d., p. 3).

The development of these illuminations and the arrival of the printing press in the 1430s also brought new possibilities, such as mass copying techniques, mechanical printing, new styles, techniques, and materials for artistic production within the bookish stories that were being created, ultimately leading to the graphic narratives that are comic books. It is also noticeable that these dialogues, despite the rudimentary form in which they are presented by modern and post-modern standards of comic book production worldwide, are, in a way, more elaborate than the mere captions in Prince Valiant comics.

A milestone in the history of comics is the work of the Swiss artist Rudolf Töpffer in the early 19th century. He created graphic stories that were criticized at the time for being childish and infamous. He did not realize that he had created a new form of artistic production. “Even so, Töpffer's contribution to the understanding of comics is considerable, if only for this realization that he who was neither artist nor writer [...] had created and mastered a form which was at one both and neither. A language all its own” (McCloud, 1995, p. 17).

There are authors, such as Guimarães (2003), who argue that comics and their development only emerged after the 19th century, including issues related to modern elements like mediation, mass production, distribution. However, this is a matter of social mass communication and media language, particularly a one-to-many communication within an increasingly mechanized and mechanistic, digital, and virtual society. But, in terms of artistic production, such as drawing, inking, coloring and publication, even if only in a single handwritten edition, the art of illuminations bears a striking resemblance to comics when produced sequentially. Not only illuminations but also other art forms, as discussed by Eisner (1989) and McCloud (1995), such as tapestries, bas-reliefs, sequential paintings, and engravings.

Thus, I question once again the status of the protagonist in Hal Foster's work, "Prince Valiant", as a comic, and, in general, among the advocates of the Ninth Art, it is affirmed that, yes, they are sequential art. We expand the question to encompass the medieval art of illuminations. Based on the elements that exist in comics or sequential art, primarily with text and images, and from these the various possibilities that are proposed, could illuminations, inserted into codices, be

⁹ Free translating from: Durante a Idade Média, os filactérios entraram nas artes plásticas na forma de faixas com mensagens ou orações escritas nas pinturas sacras. Geralmente, um santo ou anjo era seu portador. [...] Este exemplo é do ano 1240 e mostra a conversão do apóstolo Paulo. Deste momento para frente, o que ocorre é uma gradual mudança do filactério para as tentativas de encaixar textos ditos pelos personagens no desenho.

considered comics? In this regard, there may be controversy as to whether they are or are not. However, as analyzed in this paper, illuminations certainly fit the definition of sequential art.

5. CONSIDERATIONS

In this paper, my aim was to present medieval works, illuminations, images created from parchment, papyrus, and later codices, as forms of sequential art. To achieve this, it was necessary to demonstrate that comic book elements were present in the miniature productions of the medieval era, such as panels, images, text, the way text relates to space, characters, their actions, and many of the elements that are incorporated into the Ninth Art are also present in illuminated works. Thus, that form of art, beyond being purely related to books, where drawings or florals were inserted around the page, can also be considered sequential art.

In addition to discussing sequential art and comics, it was also necessary to address a theme frequently used in medieval narratives: stories of knights. A comparison with a contemporary production was made, specifically the character Prince Valiant, created in the 1930s and still in production today. Besides addressing the topic of knights' stories, the article highlights the production methods. Despite the absence of one of the elements, the speech balloon, in Prince Valiant's comics, it is evident that this absence doesn't negate its status as a comic.

With the discovery regarding the Prince Valiant comic, a historical overview of medieval illuminated art and its development over the centuries was provided. This development ranged from no images to ornamental images and, later, to more complex visual narratives, which ultimately evolved into what we now call comics.

Due to the fact that research on comics often focuses on authors, stories, or characters and appears to place less importance on studies about the historical processes of comics, I had to explore other libraries beyond articles and books directly related to this art form. Therefore, I believe that in the future, when this subject is explored by new researchers, it will be possible to emphasize that sequential art can encompass more than what has been discussed up to this point.

6. REFERENCES

Andrade, C. (2017). Príncipe Valente e a modernização do cavaleiro. *Revista ComparArte*, 1(1), 20-43. <https://revistas.ufrj.br/index.php/ca/article/view/11530/8467>. Accessed on may 20, 2023.

Barr, M. W., & Bolland, B. (1982-1985). Camelot 3000. DC Comics.

BARBIERI, Daniele (2017). AS LINGUAGENS DOS QUADRINHOS. Traduzido por Thiago de Almeida Castor do Amaral – São Paulo : Petrópolis.

Bible. Genesis 1. In: *Online Holy Bible*. Available at: https://www.bibliaon.com/genesis_1/. Accessed on May 27, 2023.

BOLSHAW, M. (nd). TEORIA NARRATIVA E ARTE SEQUENCIAL Metodologia de análise para Histórias em Quadrinhos. Published on the Academia.edu platform. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/12429504/TEORIA_NARRATIVA_E_ARTE_SEQUENCIAL_Metodologia_de_an%C3%A1lise_para_Hist%C3%B3rias_em_Quadrinhos . Accessed on January 12, 2023.

Christy, S. (2017, March 21). The many names of comics around the world! Explanation, revised and updated. Sávio Christy: musings on the arts of drawing and writing. (blog). Available at: <https://saviochristi3.blogspot.com/2017/03/os-muitos-nomes-da-historia-em.html>. Accessed on October 15, 2022.

Diniz, A., & Eder, A.(nd). *Mundo Quadrado* – Number 2 - Nona Arte Publisher: Rio de Janeiro.

Eisner, W. (1985). *Comics and Sequential Art*. Poorhouse Press.

Groensteen, T. (1999). *The System of Comics*. University Press of Mississippi.

Guimarães, E. (2003). Interação texto/imagem na história em quadrinhos. In CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE CIÊNCIAS DA COMUNICAÇÃO, 26o, Belo Horizonte, 2003. *Anais*. Belo Horizonte: Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais; Sociedade Brasileira de Estudos Interdisciplinares de Comunicação. Available at: http://www.intercom.org.br/papers/nacionais/2003/www/pdf/2003_NP16_guimaraes.pdf. Accessed on May 20, 2023.

McCloud, S. (1993). *Understanding comics: The invisible art*. HarperPerennial.

Nogueira, T. (2017) Psychomachia de Prudêncio - Estudo, tradução e texto latino. *Revista Pandora Brasil*, number 86. Faculdade de São Bento.

Paz, L. (2018). A resignificação do balão dentro do desenvolvimento das histórias em quadrinhos como forma cultural. In: JORNADAS INTERNACIONAIS DE HISTÓRIAS EM QUADRINHOS, 5as, São Paulo, Escola de comunicações de Artes da Universidade de São Paulo. 2018. *Anais*. São Paulo: ECA-USP, 2018. Available at: https://jornadas.eca.usp.br/anais/5asjornadas/q_historia/liber_paz.pdf. Accessed on June 21, 2023.

Rupes Magazine. *Rupes ensina arte sequencial e os quadrinhos* [Blog]. Available at: <https://rupesmagazine.tumblr.com/post/634798506387881984/rupes-ensina-arte-sequencial-e-os-quadrinhos>. Accessed on february 25, 2023.

Significados. *Spin-off*. Retrieved March 2, 2023, from <https://www.significados.com.br/spin-off/>

Vianna, L. (2016). A historiografia medieval e a escrita da História: os objetos impressos do Livro dos Feitos (1557). *Diálogos* 3(20). 30-41. Available at: <https://periodicos.uem.br/ojs/index.php/Dialogos/article/view/33669/pdf>. Accessed on may 20, 2023.

Visalli, A. Godoi, P. (2023). Estudos sobre imagens medievais: o caso das iluminuras. *Diálogos*. 3(20). 129-144. Available at: <https://periodicos.uem.br/ojs/index.php/Dialogos/article/view/33669/pdf>. Accessed on may 20, 2023.

Xavier, G. (2019). HISTÓRIAS EM QUADRINHOS: panorama histórico, características e verbo-visualidade. *Darandina Revisteletrônica*. Programa de Pós-Graduação em Letras: estudos Literários. 2(10). Universidade Federal de Juiz Fora.